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Judicial Review in Sweden in the Context of Migration Law: Control Mechanisms and Human Rights Challenges

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Judicial review can play a crucial role in safeguarding the rule of law, democratic procedures and human rights protections. In Sweden, the question of judicial review is particularly important in the field of migration law, a domain shaped by rapid legislative reforms, increasing political pressure and power, and heightened human rights concerns. Swedish judicial review has a distinct character, as it involves both ex ante review of legislative proposals and post ante review of legal acts.

The Swedish Judicial Review Model

Sweden's system of judicial review is decentralised. While Sweden does not have a constitutional court, all courts and even administrative authorities may refuse to apply legislation found to violate the Constitution, EU law, or the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR). Courts may therefore disapply legislation, but they lack the power to strike down or invalidate legal acts.¹

Historically, courts were substantially constrained. Prior to the 2010 reform, the Instrument of Government allowed courts to set aside a legal act only where the error was 'manifest'. This so-called 'manifest requirement' created a high threshold for declaring legislation

¹ See The Instrument of Government 11:14 and 12:10.

unconstitutional and embodied a restrictive judicial review culture, permitting judicial intervention only in clear and obvious cases.²

Despite this broad institutional distribution, judicial review in Sweden is substantively constrained. The Instrument of Government (*Regeringsformen*) emphasises the democratic credentials of the Parliament (*Riksdagen*). It provides that ‘when reviewing a statute under the first paragraph, special consideration shall be given to the fact that the Riksdag is the foremost representative of the people and that the Constitution takes precedence over ordinary law’.³ This provision reflects a strong commitment to parliamentary sovereignty and limits the scope of judicial intervention. It illustrates the strong emphasis on parliamentary sovereignty and trust in the legislative process. This separation of powers philosophy shapes how rights-sensitive issues are adjudicated.

Ex Ante Review

The primary ex ante mechanism of judicial review in Sweden is the scrutiny performed by the Council on Legislation (Lagrådet), which assesses draft legislation for compatibility with constitutional norms, rule-of-law standards, and human rights obligations. Its opinions, however, are advisory and non-binding.⁴

This limitation becomes evident in the case of recent migration reforms. Government Bill 2020/21:191 introduced significant changes, making temporary residence permits the norm for refugees and subsidiary protection beneficiaries, tightening conditions for permanent residence, and restricting family reunification rights. These reforms triggered substantial human rights concerns, particularly regarding proportionality, stability of residence, and the best interests of the child. Although Lagrådet raised several critical remarks, the government and Parliament proceeded largely unchanged. Thus, ex ante review in Sweden, while institutionally present, does not function as a strong barrier to rights-restrictive migration legislation. The political branches retain considerable freedom to reshape migration law even when human rights implications are substantial.

Post Ante Review

Post ante judicial review occurs primarily through appeals against decisions of the Swedish Migration Agency. Migration Courts and the Migration Court of Appeal assess whether decisions comply with statutory provisions, constitutional norms, EU law, and the ECHR. This mechanism allows individualized human rights considerations—such as family life, non-refoulement, or the best interests of the child—to be raised and evaluated.

There are important strengths in this system. Courts have the authority to disapply legislation that conflicts with higher norms. Judicial review can potentially mitigate some of the harsh effects of restrictive migration laws. It depends on judicial choices in engaging in explicit constitutional review. The philosophy of functionalism may lead courts to defer to legislative choices and avoid limiting the democratic room for manoeuvre of Parliament. Thus, while post ante review exists in principle as a safeguard, in practice its protective capacity may be constrained.

² See H Wenander, ‘Administrative Constitutional Review in Sweden: Between Subordination and Independence’ 2020 *European Public Law*; J Nergelius, ‘Konstitutionellt rättighetsskydd. Svensk rätt i ett komparativt perspektiv’ (Norstedts Juridik, 1996).

³ The Instrument of Government 1:4.

⁴ See The Instrument of Government Chapter 8.

Human Rights Challenges and Judicial Limits

Sweden's migration law has, over the past decade, moved in an increasingly restrictive direction. The Tidö Agreement (2022) between the government parties and the Sweden Democrats sets the political foundation for a “paradigm shift” toward stricter migration and integration policies.⁵ While measures such as temporary residence permits and stricter family reunification requirements create increased insecurity, particularly for children, they are justified as necessary to maintain system capacity and meet minimum legal obligations, thus narrowing rights while claiming compliance with EU and international law.⁶ In this context, the limitations of both ex-ante and post ante judicial review heighten the risk that human rights violations may go unchallenged. Ex ante review by the Council on Legislation provides only weak protection, as its opinions are non-binding. Post ante review through the courts offers more individualized assessment but is limited by institutional restraint and practical barriers to access. As Sweden continues to reform its migration legislation, the effectiveness of judicial review in protecting human rights comes into sharper focus.

⁵ Sverigedemokraterna, Moderaterna, Kristdemokraterna, Liberalerna, *Tidöavtalet: Överenskommelse för Sverige*, <https://www.liberalerna.se/wp-content/uploads/tidoavtalet-overenskommelse-for-sverige-slutlig.pdf>, Accessed 15 December 2025.

⁶ Prop. 2020/21:191 chapter 5.